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HEALTH HAZARDS OF PULP AND PAPER INDUSTRIALS WORKERS

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ABSTRACT

The paper reviews the available literature regarding the work environment in pulp and paper mills and the risk for malignant disease, lung cancer, skin problems, respiratory disease, fibrotic disease, autoimmune disease, nasal irritation and cardiac disease indicating that this occupational group was exposed to asbestos, chlorine compounds, wood dusts, formaldehyde, organic solvents, terpens, latex, clay, carboxy methyl cellulose and silica etc. although inconsistent cancer mortality rates have also been found into a retrospective workers in the paper and pulp industry. The over exposure of calcium carbonate dust can cause irritation of eyelids, redness of eye, tearing and pain in eyes, runny nose, sneezing, coughing, nasal irritation and physical irritant of the eyes, nose, mucous membrane and skin of humans. Silica has been long known to cause progressive granulomatous and fibrotic disease in the lung in human and its affects DNA by binding directly with DNA or indirectly by promoting growth of already initiated cells. To conclude the use of toxic chemicals for pulping and bleaching paper can lead to the pollution that cause negative impacts on the health of paper industry workers. The release of toxic pollutants likes chlorine, lead, mercury and phosphorous into the environment by the industry could be responsible for the genetic damage in industry workers.

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INTRODUCTION

Industrialization and environment

Pollution is the introduction of contaminants into an environment that causes instability, disorder, harm or discomfort to the ecosystem (i.e.) physical system or living organisms. Pollution can take the form of chemical substances or energy, such as noise, heat or light energy. Pollutants, the elements of pollution, can be foreign substances or energies or naturally occurring; when naturally occurring, they are considered as contaminants when they exceed natural levels. Pollution is often clarified as point source or non point source pollution (Gari, 2002).

The fast pace of industrialization, galloping demand for energy and reckless exploitation of natural resources during the last century have been mainly responsible for aggravating the problem of environmental pollution, which is now set to pose serious threat to biodiversity and ecosystem process (De, 2007). The important environmental issues that was included as environmental health hazards and diseases of new millennium; disasters management and mitigation and application of remote sensing and GIS for disaster management and environmental studies. The total Indian population suffers from allergic disorders due to the environmental pollution such as allergic rhinitis, bronchial asthma, atopic dermatitis etc (Babar, 2007).

The impact of toxic releases from pulp and paper industry, focusing on serious public health risks faced by people living in proximity to those mills (Bailey and Newland, 2000). The literature was focused to assess the health status among paper industry workers. The main objectives of the literature were Assessment of Hematological and biochemical parameters in paper industry workers, Assessment of enzymic antioxidant status and Detection of DNA damage.

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF PAPER INDUSTRY

Production of paper

The production of pulp and paper is an important industrial trade. This work environment entails a variety of exposure depending on the process. The pulp process have been the alkaline sulfate process, mechanical processes, the acidic sulfite process, and during the last few decades waste paper pulping as well. The main occupational exposures have been wood dust, terpenes and bleaching chemicals in the pulp mills. In sulfate mills also hydrogen sulfide and other reduced sulfur compounds are used. In sulfite mills sulfur dioxide is found as well, whereas paper dust and different additives appear in the paper mills. There is a multitude of chemicals in this industry, including some potential carcinogens. Other exposures are noise, heat, microorganisms and shift works (Andersson, *et al.*, 2002).

Paper is manufactured from chemicals and mechanical pulp on one hand and recycled fibers on the other. Both have environmental impacts but in different ways. Paper production requires large amount of water, but most of the water used is recycled it leads to the environmental pollution. The raw material such as old news papers, woods and chemicals used for the production of paper are considered as environmental impacts and environmental health hazards to human

In the paper and paper board mills, the raw material used for the manufacture of paper and paper boards are old news papers, manifold white ledger, coated book stock, sorted office papers etc. The most of the agents were measured in the pulping and refining departments and in on-machine coating and winding of papers/paper boards are asbestos, carbon dioxide, nitrous oxides, sulfur dioxides, carbon monoxides minerals dusts, paper dusts, chlorine compounds, sulphuric acid, styrene, terpenes, and different organic solvents (Koheran *et al.*, 2004). Conventional deinking requires large amount of chemicals such as NaOH, NaSO₃, H₂O₂, etc. cellulose acts on the cellulose fibers and facilitates the loosening of the ink from the fibre (Tandon *et al.*, 2005).

PROPERTIES AND APPLICATIONS OF CHEMICAL AGENTS USED

Carboxy methyl cellulose and carboxy methyl starch are polymers which are easily to handle. Carboxy methylation of polysaccharide is a widely studied conversion since it is simple and leads to products with a variety of promising properties (Heinze and Liebert, 2001). In general, polysaccharides is activated with aqueous alkali hydroxide mostly sodium hydroxide and converted with monochloroacetic acid or its sodium salt according to the Williamson ether synthesis yielding the carboxy methyl polysaccharide derivatives (Heinze, 2005).

Carboxy methyl cellulose is soluble in either cold or hot water and insoluble in organic solvents. Carboxy methyl cellulose can be even dissolved in formic acid with comparatively slight chain degradation (Fannon *et al.*, 2004). One of the most important goals of carboxy methylation of cellulose and starch is to obtain water-soluble derivatives which are applied in various fields in order to control the behavior of aqueous system and preparations. They behave as typical polyelectrolytes (Jardeyby, 2004).

Carboxy methyl cellulose and starch is used as example to stabilize clay and latex systems. The carboxy methyl cellulose is of interest for metal ion adsorption, e.g., in waste water treatment. Special points of interest are the interactions between the carboxylic moieties and poly valent metal cations and the selectivity of these interactions. An interesting area of application of their gels is cell immobilization and controlled release of bioactive compounds (Fischer, *et al.*, 2002). This controlled drug release was investigated with carboxy methyl cellulose. The polymer was used as carrier for, e.g. erythromycin as model drug. The carboxy methyl cellulose was cross linked with ferric salt to get biodegradable beads. Carboxy methyl cellulose is applied as disintegration aid for tablets (Heinze, 2005).

The macroscopic properties of polymers solutions are determined by microscopic (molecular) parameters. For example, the viscosity of the solution of carboxy methyl cellulose and carboxy methyl starch is influenced by the molar mass of the polymers, their degree of branching, and their radius of gyration, R_g , as well as their flexibility. Thickening properties of the solutions are related to the rigidity of the polymer backbone, which can be characterized by the persistence length. The intrinsic persistence length of carboxy methyl cellulose determined by SEC-MALLS as well as by potentiometric titrations with DS in the range from 0.75-1.25 applying the worm like theory is assessed to be 16nm irrespective of the DS (Kubala, *et al.*, 2003).

There are different grades of carboxy methyl cellulose and carboxy methyl starch. Especially the highly purified products (i.e.) of low salt content have made the carboxy methyl polysaccharides to valuable additive in many areas of application including the food and pharmaceutical areas (Spange, 2003). The importance of carboxy methylation of polysaccharides will further increase in the context of increasing use of renewable resources (i.e.) in the context of sustainable development on one hand. On the other hand, polysaccharide possess unique structures synthesized by nature that are an excellent basis of the development of advanced and highly engineered products for present and future applications (Lazik, *et al.*, 2002).

The calcium carbonate is non combustible, odorless, white powder or colorless crystalline solid. It occurs naturally in the minerals aragonite, calcite, limestone, marble and vaterite. The two forms of calcium carbonate that are important commercially are aragonite and calcite. The molecular weight of calcium carbonate is 100.9 and it is insoluble in water and alcohol and is soluble in dilute acids (NLM, 1991). The synonyms of calcium carbonate are aragonite, agricultural limestone, agstone, bell mine, pulverized limestone, calcite, chalk, domolite fraklin, limestone, marble, portlant, stone, lithographic stone and sohhofen stone (ACGIH, 1991).

Calcium carbonate used as a neutralizing agents, filters and extender in rubber, plastic and paint products and as an opacification agent in paper products. It is also used in the manufacture of putty, tooth powders, antacide, white wash, quick lime, Portland cement, dentifrices, ceramics, polishes, inks, foods, pharmaceuticals, antibiotics, adhesive etc. It is used in removing sulfur dioxides from stack gases and as a metallurgical flux. It is used as a pigment and as a source of lime. It is used as an antacid in human. It is used as a dietary supplement as a nutrient and as an anti-diarrheal agent (U.S. Department of Health and Human Service, 1995).

Formaldehyde is the main component used in the paper or paper board industry. High concentration of formaldehyde forms many kinds of coating and laminating chemicals occurred in calendaring area and in the on-machine coating of paper. Formaldehyde is a flammable and colorless gas. Formaldehyde is used in the production of resins, molding compounds, photographic films, decorative laminates, and plywood, and as a bactericide and a tissue preservative (Hauptmann, *et al.*, 2003). Formaldehyde is highly reactive at the site of contact and the anatomical features of respiratory tract and the patterns of flow of inhaled air are quite different between rats and humans. DNA protein cross linkage formation, cytotoxicity, adaptive changes, epithelial cell proliferation, preneoplasia. Lesions and tumors are described to occur in response to inhaled formaldehyde (Duhayon, *et al.*, 2008).

Formaldehyde is an important industrial chemical that has been used for more than 60 years in the manufacture of resins, adhesives, and plastics. It has also been used in the processing of anatomic and pathologic specimens, as an antimicrobial agent in cosmetics, as a fumigant in agriculture, and in the production of crease-resistant garments. Although the heaviest exposures to formaldehyde have occurred occupationally, it is also encountered residentially, where it arises from several sources, including particle board made with formaldehyde-based resins (which are widely used in furniture) and cavity insulation with urea formaldehyde foam (Coggon, *et al.*, 2003).

The term "solvents" represents a diverse collection of liquid compounds with different chemical properties including alcohols, glycols, aromatic hydrocarbons (e.g., benzene, toluene, and xylene) and chlorinated product such as carbon tetra chloride and trichloroethylene. Solvents are used extensively as degreasers and cleansers in many settings (e.g., cleaning metal in a variety of industries, dry cleaning establishments) but the specific type of solvent varies substantially across types of workplace involved in similar activities. Solvents are generally metabolized quickly so that biologic measurements reflect short term rather than long term or cumulative exposure (Cooper and Parks, 2004).

Organic solvents such as xylene, toluene, styrene and benzene are most widely used in paper industry which is considered as health hazards. These polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons are a large group of organic compounds with two or more fused aromatic rings. They have a relatively low solubility in water, but are highly lipophilic. Most of the poly aromatic hydrocarbons with low vapour pressure in the air are adsorbed on particles. When dissolved in water or adsorbed on particulate matter, poly aromatic hydrocarbons can undergo photodecomposition when exposed to ultra violet light from solar radiation (Srogi, 2007). Solvents are used extensively as degreasers and cleansers in many settings such as cleaning metals and dry cleaning etc. Trichloroethylene (TCE) is a solvent used in numerous industries, as degreaser in the metal manufacturing industry, solvent for oils and resins, or the production of rubber and as a chemical intermediate in the production of refrigerants. A number of epidemiological studies have investigated the association between exposure to trichloroethylene and renal cell cancer but the results have been inconsistent (Charbotel, *et al.*, 2007).

Asbestos refers to a variety of hydroxylated; silicated asbestos minerals are divided into two broad groups serpentine and amphibole. Serpentine asbestos is called chrysotile, while amphibole family includes crocidolite, anthophyllite, amosite, actinolite and tremolite. These minerals are said to exist in an asbestos form of fibrosis habit when the mineral has grown in one dimension to form long thin crystals. Asbestos is a form of diffuse interstitial pulmonary fibrosis. It is caused by inhalation of excessive amount of asbestos fibers that are within certain size and aerodynamic shape ranges. It can cause significant impairment or even death, and is a well recognized risk factor for the development of lung cancer (Ross, 2009).

Vinyl chloride, acrylonitrile and styrene are important industrial chemicals with a large number of applications. Vinyl chloride is mainly used in the manufacture of poly vinyl chloride, acrylonitrile is used in the manufacture of acrylic and modacrylic fibers, resins, elastomers and rubbers, and styrene is used in the production of many important commercial polymers, including poly styrene, polyesters, styrene butadiene and in the manufacture of fiberglass-reinforced products. Acrylonitrile and styrene are also used together in the production of styrene-acrylonitrile and acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene resins. Inhalation is the primary route of exposure to these substances, although acrylonitrile exposure can also occur through dermal contact (Scelo, *et al.*, 2004).

Silica is among the most common minerals on earth. It exists in two forms, crystalline and amorphous. Crystalline form is also called as free silica. Crystalline silica has evidence that it causes lung fibrosis or cancer whereas amorphous silica has no evidence that it causes diseases. Low exposure may occur with whenever it mixed with dust it is sufficient to cause disease (Cooper and Parks, 2004). Silica and asbestos are also mainly used in production of fibers, ceramics, plywood, bricks etc. the use as asbestos has been increasingly restricted as its dangers have been well recognized (Luce *et al.*, 2002).

TOXICOLOGICAL EFFECTS

The proposal that exposures to environmental or occupational substances may affect erection ability is a tenable one and would add to a growing list of pathogenic risk factors associated with erectile dysfunction (Park, *et al.*, 2008). Several lines of evidence by clinical, epidemiological and biomedical research investigation lend support. Several environmental toxicants to include lead, organic solvents, formaldehyde, asbestos, sulphur dioxide, nitrogen dioxide have been implicated as possibly hazardous agents. Effects on the nervous and hormonal systems have been proposed as the leading mechanisms by which environmental toxicants adversely impact erectile function (Burnett, 2008).

Formaldehyde is mutagenic and when inhaled at high concentration and it is carcinogenic. Some epidemiologic studies have linked occupational exposure to formaldehyde with cancers of the nose, nasopharynx and lung, but the evidence for human carcinogenicity has been inconsistent and requires clarification. Formaldehyde is mutagenic *in vitro*, and exposures *in vivo* by gavage and inhalation have been shown to induce cytogenetic damage in tissues that are in direct contact with the chemical. When rats inhaled formaldehyde at concentrations of 14 ppm or higher, they developed cancer of the nose but it is unclear whether these tumors arose through a genotoxic mechanism or as a consequence of cytotoxicity. Epidemiologic studies of occupational exposure to formaldehyde have suggested elevated risks of cancer at various sites, including the nose and nasal sinuses, nasopharynx, lung, and brain. However, the evidence that formaldehyde is carcinogenic in humans has been inconsistent, and when last reviewed by the International Agency for Research on Cancer in 1995, the evidence was classed as "limited" (Coggon, *et al.*, 2003).

Asbestos was the earliest and is the most widely recognized carcinogenic hazard. It being carcinogenic to humans based on both sufficient toxicological and epidemiological evidence (Mossman, *et al.*, 2007). It is known that silica is toxic to pulmonary macrophages which engulf the silica particles and a variety of chemotactic and toxic substances released from lysed macrophages result in the collagen production which causes fibrosis. Silica is a human carcinogen (Luce, *et al.*, 2002).

Organic solvents such as polyaromatic hydrocarbons and also considered as human carcinogenic and mutagenic agents which will possess lung mortality disease and cancers who are exposed to it (Srogi, 2007). Poly aromatic hydro carbons comprise the largest class of chemical compounds known to be cancer causing agents. Some, while not carcinogenic, may act as synergist. Some of these are manufactured for research or used in medicines, dyes, plastics and pesticides such as naphthalene found in mothballs. Poly aromatic hydrocarbons can also found in coal tar, bitumen, crude oil, and creosote and roofing tar. Thus, potential exposure to chemicals may be assessed by testing contaminated soil, air or water for the chemicals of interest and estimating the degree of intake of each of these media into the human body (Lichtfouse *et al.*, 2005).

The paper industry is a major source of toxic chemicals used which lead to pollution. Many toxic chemicals are used in paper making, especially toxic solvents and chlorine compounds used to bleach and delignify pulp. Additional toxins are used as biocides to prevent bacterial growth in pulp and finished paper products (Yadav, 2006).

PAPER INDUSTRY ON HUMAN HEALTH

The health effect of workers in the pulp and paper industry revealed that high exposure of chemicals used was associated with an increased prevalence of impaired lung function, allergic disease respiratory disease and death (Korhonen *et al.*, 2004).

Exposure deriving from emission on the part of paper, pulp and board industries involves complex mixtures. Most studies connected with their possible influence on lung cancer pertain to the field of occupational exposure (Corella *et al.*, 2008). The risk association between environmental exposure and erectile dysfunction can be further characterized by several specific risk relationships. Type of exposure, dose response effect, effect of risk factor covarities and effects of discontinuation of exposure represent such disease correlates. As suggested by the aforementioned section, various types of environmental exposure apparently correlate with erectile dysfunction. Passive exposure to cigarette smoke, which contains numerous pollutants, represents a further example of a type of environmental exposure that has been shown to be a risk factor for erectile dysfunction (Burnett, 2008).

Formaldehyde at a concentration of approximately 0.5-1.0 ppm causes acute health effects including irritation of the eye and upper airway mucosa. Inhalation of the formaldehyde develops squamous cell carcinomas of the nasal cavity. Human leukocytes exposed to formaldehyde developed DNA-protein cross links *in vitro* and *in vivo* which may result in loss of genetic material and leads to nasopharyngeal cancer and local irritation (Hildesheim, 2001). Exposure of the formaldehyde has reportedly been associated with Leukemia, especially in three broad occupational groups: embalmers, anatomists, and formaldehyde industrial workers (Descatha *et al.*, 2004).

Silica has been long known to cause progressive granulomatous and fibrotic disease in the lung in human and it affects DNA by binding directly with DNA or indirectly by promoting growth of already initiated cells (Luce *et al.*, 2002). Silica can cause chromosomal aberrations and transformation in mammalian cells. There have been a large number of epidemiologic investigations that studies of silica exposed workers suggest an increased lung cancer but they are not consistent. Silica dust exposure leads to autoimmune disease such as systemic lupus erythematosus (Cooper and Parks, 2004).

Asbestos has the potential to induce lung tumor and mesotheliomas. Pathological asbestos is associated with a significant increase in lung cancer risk. The exact risk of lung cancer that is associated with asbestos is depends on many factors that have not yet been completely elucidated. These may include exposure amount, intensity, duration, and host factors. The degree of fibrosis, fiber type and smoking history also play a significant role. The prevalence of pathological asbestosis has not been accurately determined for asbestos exposed workers. Pathological asbestosis is associated with a significant increase in lung cancer. In one study, an approximate fivefold increase in lung cancer was found among persons who are continuously exposed to asbestos (Ross, 2009).

Other forms of diffuse interstitial pulmonary fibrosis, which are pathologically similar to asbestosis, also are associated with an increase risk of lung cancer. For example, in a study of people with diffuse interstitial pulmonary fibrosis associated with scleroderma, the lung cancer risk was five times that of control subjects (Bouros *et al.*, 2002).

Very high fibre inhalation exposure has been measured while people were wearing. Personal protective equipment manufactured from chrysotile asbestos. However, there is little data that relates specifically to wearing asbestos gloves or mitts, particularly when used in hot environments such as those found in glass manufacturing. The aim of this study was to assess the likely personal exposure to asbestos fibres when asbestos mitts were used. Asbestos protective clothing was widely used in "hot" industries such as foundries, steel plants and glassworks, and by fire fighters. Undoubtedly the use of such clothing has saved many lives and made the working conditions of others more bearable. Use of asbestos protective clothing was considered acceptable in the UK until the late 1970s and, for example, it was not until 1976 that Scottish health civil servants advised the fire service of the possible hazards posed by asbestos equipment used by fire fighters. At that time it was concluded that although the risks to health were minimal, fire brigades should phase out their use and find replacement gloves made from alternative materials (Cherrie, *et al.*, 2005).

The over exposure of calcium carbonate dust can cause irritation of eyelids, redness of eye, tearing and pain in eyes, runny nose, sneezing, coughing and nasal irritation. Calcium carbonate dust is a physical irritant of the eyes, nose, mucous membrane and skin of humans. Contact of calcium carbonate dust with eyes causes redness, pain and inflammation of the eyelids while contact with the skin causes local irritation of moderate degree. Exposure to large amount of the dust of this substance causes coughing, sneezing and nasal irritation. Although chronic exposure to pure calcium carbonate does not cause pneumoconiosis, similar exposure to impure limestone (calcium carbonate) containing 3% to 20% quartz may pose a silicosis risk (NLM 1991).

Calcium carbonate causes moderate to severe irritation in contact with the tissues of animals. Instilled into rabbit's eyes, calcium carbonate causes severe irritation. In contact with the skin of rabbits for 24 hours, this substance caused moderate irritation. The oral LD₅₀ in rats is 6,450mg/kg (NIOSH, 1991).

Most of the epidemiologic studies pertaining to solvents and systematic autoimmune disease have focused on systemic sclerosis and undifferentiated connective tissues. But in contrast there was no association between occupational exposure to solvents and systemic lupus erythematosus in a recent case control study. Renal Cell Carcinoma (RCC), the most frequent malignancy in the adult kidney, is usually sporadic. The phenotype is extremely heterogeneous and several classifications of renal epithelial tumours have been proposed. Main histological subtypes of renal epithelial tumours include clear-cell RCC (75%), papillary RCC (10–15%), chromophobe RCC (5%) and oncocytomas (5%). Inactivation of the *VHL* tumour suppressor gene is thought to result both in development of tumours in the von Hippel-Lindau (VHL) disease (MIM #19330) and in sporadic clear-cell RCC. Germ line mutations of *VHL* gene are responsible for VHL disease, a rare dominantly inherited cancer syndrome predisposing to a number of highly vascularized tumours including multiple clear-cell RCC whereas somatic mutation or methylation of *VHL* gene is a frequent event in sporadic clear-cell RCC (Charbotel *et al.*, 2007).

Increased lung function and respiratory symptoms among workers exposed to paper dust. In addition asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease has been found among workers exposed to soft paper dust (Korhonen *et al.*, 2004). The evidence for malignant disease in pulp and paper mills was reported that increased risk for lung cancer among workers exposed to asbestos, chlorine compounds, wood dusts, formaldehyde, organic solvents, terpenes, latex, clay, carboxy methyl cellulose and silica etc. although inconsistent cancer mortality rates have also been found in a retrospective study of workers in the paper and pulp industry (Scelo *et al.*, 2004).

Vinyl chloride is an established cause of angiosarcoma of the liver; a few studies have reported a significant excess of lung cancer among exposed workers, although the overall evidence is inadequate. Moreover, vinyl chloride has been shown to cause lung cancer in animals. Some studies reported slightly elevated risk of lung cancer among acrylonitrile exposed workers (Bernnan and Bray, 2002).

Lung cancer is the leading cause of cancer related death among men and women who lived near paper and paper board industries. In layer the male workers in pulp and paper mills, an increased mortality rate for malignant cancer was found (Spitz *et al.*, 2006). Those malignancies were associated with the following known or suspected carcinogens to which the workers were exposed such as asbestos cause's pleura, formaldehyde leads to kidney, brain effects and Hodgkin's disease (Corella, *et al.*, 2008).

Epidemiological studies have reported positive associations between NHL and certain occupations including those of farmers, pesticide applicators, drivers and managers. Several studies have reported no association between development of NHL and the agricultural occupations (farmers, agricultural and forestry workers and pesticide applicators. Occupational exposures of a prior interest include pesticides, dusts (metal, wood, paper etc), paints, diesel exhaust fumes, cleaning fluids, cutting oils and solvents. In this paper, we examined the association between NHL and (1) selected long term occupations, and (2) occupational exposures based on an individual's occupational history, and (3) duration of employment (Karunanayake *et al.*, 2008). Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma (NHL) is a cancer of the lymphatic system. Even though NHL is a relatively rare disease, its incidence rates have been increasing worldwide for both men and women. A number of factors, including inherited and acquired immunodeficiency states as well as infectious, physical, and chemical agents have been associated with an increased risk for NHL (Fisher *et al.*, 2005).

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